

ISic3521

I.Sicily inscription 3521

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis of San Placido, sep.40

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3559

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI313642

1. Ίουλία
2. Μαρκία
3. χρηστή
4. χάρει.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493853

EDCS 38200010

PHI 313642

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 14
Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 166

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